

The cultural ecosystem services provided by different types of urban green spaces

Marlon Sippel

12642355

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Examiner: Dr. Verena Seufert

Assessor: Dr. A.C. (Harry) Seijmonsbergen

UNIVERSITEIT VAN AMSTERDAM

Instituut voor Biodiversiteit en
Ecosysteem Dynamica

 IVM Institute for
Environmental Studies

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Abstract

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The increasing population density of cities worldwide makes it more and more important to understand what aspects of the urban landscape are of particular value to the residents. One aspect that is often overlooked in this context are urban green spaces, which are linked to a multitude of indirect benefits to the residents of cities. One potential reason for this is that the value of urban green space is hardly quantifiable. This is largely caused by the fact that of all the ecosystem services that nature provides, cultural ecosystem services are disproportionately important and at the same time the most vaguely defined ecosystem service. To understand and quantify the cultural value of urban green spaces it is thus necessary to investigate cultural values, extract the benefits they serve and connect them to the activities that people perform. In the next step, to not only link urban green spaces to cultural service provision, but also understand how urban green spaces provide such values, it is essential to also analyse urban green spaces and differentiate between different types. An improved understanding on what people value about urban green spaces could be instrumental for future urban planning to improve urban green space designs and cater to a broader audience. In this study I apply a novel approach towards assessing the cultural ecosystem services that are provided by urban green spaces in Amsterdam. By identifying the supply of different types of vegetation within the urban environment, as well as different activities linked to cultural ecosystem service provision, a detailed analysis on the benefits of urban green spaces is made possible. Through the creation of questionnaire derived spatial user preference indication maps, it was possible to find out where people go to pursue certain activities. Additionally, by applying state of the art light detection and ranging (LiDAR) technology, I created a highly accurate vegetation typology map that can be applied to the entire urban landscape. Performance of spatial statistics found that people have an overall preference to perform outdoor activities in areas with higher vegetation cover. A higher diversity of land-types was also found to positively affect which areas people seek to pursue cultural ecosystem service related activities. However, this approach is not limited to the general assessment of user preferences. Due to the diversity of activities identified, it was possible to analyse how specific vegetation types relate to the performance of certain activities, which in turn gave insight into how different vegetation types provide cultural ecosystem services. This detailed analysis showed for example that sport activities are more often related to areas with high tree cover, while for calming activities areas with dense tree and bushland cover were preferred. Application of this new approach could be a valuable next step towards understanding how urban green spaces could be improved to better cater to the demands of people living in the cities of the future.

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List of abbreviations

The following list contains all abbreviations and acronyms used in this thesis. Furthermore, it explains the meaning and refers to the page in which each term is defined or first used. The order of the list is based on the order in which the abbreviations occur throughout this study.

Abbreviation	Meaning	Page
UGS	urban green spaces	6
ES	ecosystem services	6
CES	cultural ecosystem services	6
LiDAR	light detection and ranging	7
RES	regulating ecosystem services	8
PES	provisional ecosystem services	9
NDVI	normalised difference vegetation index	11
PLAND	percentage of land	17
SIDI	Simpson's index of diversity	17
UPS	user preference score	17
NUPS	normalised user score	17

1. Introduction

It is expected that the number of people living in cities worldwide will increase from 757 million in 2010 to 2.3 billion in 2100 (Hoorweg and Pope, 2014). The effects of such a rapid demographical change are yet to be fully understood, but urban planning towards a sustainable and healthy urban society is more important than ever before. Successfully accommodating increasing numbers of people in cities while providing the chance to live a healthy and fulfilling life to all residents, is one core challenge that city planners worldwide must tackle in the 21st century.

One city that has embraced that challenge and announced steps to approach it is Amsterdam. The municipality of Amsterdam announced that they plan to have 52,500 new apartments under construction by 2025 (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2018). To align this densification with sustainable city development, the city plans to transition into a circular economy model by the year 2050 (Gemeente Amsterdam, 2020). These goals are ambitious and the question if Amsterdam can accommodate more people and reduce CO₂-emissions as well as waste simultaneously, will be seen in the future.

One factor that could be of core importance for Amsterdam's success in achieving their goals is their vegetation management. Not only does urban vegetation reduce net CO₂-emissions of a city, it also affects public health positively (Konijnendijk et al., 2013). Due to climate change, urban temperature is expected to increase by up to 30% (McCarthy et al., 2010). Urban green spaces (UGS) reduce such heat stress and also mitigate flooding (Feyisa et al., 2014; Zhang et al., 2015). Furthermore, due to the inherent cultural values of UGS, they were found to positively affect both the physical and mental health of residents (Wolch et al., 2011; Wood et al., 2017). It has also been suggested that the development of UGS can be beneficial to a cities' aim in establishing a circular economy (Chowdhury et al., 2020). Although positive effects of UGS are widely accepted in society as well as the scientific community, evidence shows that the per capita availability of UGS across European cities, decreased as a result of urban densification (Fuller and Gaston, 2009). Given these benefits, it seems odd that city planning more often than not fails to implement UGS development in new building projects.

One reason for this decrease in per capita UGS across Europe could be because the above mentioned dynamic between urban vegetation and it's users is highly complex and hardly quantifiable (Hunter and Luck, 2015). To understand this dynamic better, we must look closer into the factors at play. Not only is it important to consider the vegetation structure (e.g. UGS size, management intensity), but we must also understand how these differences are perceived by people and what the differences are between demographical groups (Palliwoda and Priess, 2021). To describe such complex relationships, models which simplify reality and enable predictions on what parameters lead to certain outcomes can be applied. In order to apply a model that assesses what vegetation types people seek within UGS to pursue certain activities, both the environment and the preference of the people exposed to it must be included as parameters.

Ecosystem services (ES) are the most common and widely respected tool to assess the value of ecosystems, which are commonly divided into the four subgroups; provisioning, regulating, cultural and supporting services (Leemans and De Groot, 2003). Of those services the maybe least understood group is cultural ecosystem services (CES), which are the most complicated of those groups to assess (Jennings et al., 2016). This is likely caused by the fact that CES describe benefits of ecosystems which are "(...) the nonmaterial benefits people obtain from ecosystems through spiritual enrichment, cognitive development, reflection, recreation, and aesthetic experiences (...)" (Leemans and De Groot, 2003). This makes them intangible in nature and hard to quantify. To gain insight into what CES people receive from UGS, research has often tried to assess the value of vegetation based on parameters derived from literature, or to assign a monetary value to the services provided (Derkzen et al., 2015; van Zoest and Hopman, 2014).

While these approaches are widely respected for most ecosystem assessments, for CES such approaches often lack evidence for how they quantify individual parameters (Hernández-Morcillo et al., 2013).

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A review on existing CES assessments found that the most common ways to analyse CES provision from UGS is through questionnaires, qualitative analysis and/or using geographical information systems (GIS); (Kabisch et al., 2015). Application of questionnaires has shown promising success in providing a valuable understanding of how people perceive and use their neighbourhood. However, Caynes et al. (2016) pointed out that in order to connect the CES to UGS, it is important to assess the fine scale, three-dimensional structure of the vegetation within UGS (Caynes et al., 2016). This is because people experiencing UGS are exposed to the vertical structure of vegetation, so taking their perspective is the ideal approach to describing vegetation accurately (Caynes et al., 2016).

Most research that assessed the value of UGS to people looked at wide scale characteristics such as tree (canopy) cover, which does not consider the vertical structure of vegetation (Dobbs et al., 2013; Shanahan et al., 2015). Another common approach was the comparison of parks to each other (Jahani and Saffariha, 2020; Özgüner, 2011). In recent years, the assessment of the vertical composition of vegetation using remote sensing has become possible due to the development and increasing availability of light detection and ranging (LiDAR) technology. LiDAR technology is an active remote sensing technology, which is produced using a drone or plane which have light sensors attached (Bakx et al., 2019). These sensors calculate the distance of any given object to the sensor using light pulses by converting the time it takes for the reflection to return to the sensor into a measure of distance (Bakx et al., 2019). Because light pulses can partially penetrate vegetation, the sensor often measures returns not only from the canopy, but often also from the understory, which makes it highly suitable for the fine-scale assessment of vertical vegetation structure (Brock et al., 2002). In geomorphology as well as forestry, models applying LiDAR data to classify vegetation, have already shown success (e.g. Alberti et al., 2013; Brodu and Lague, 2012). Although there seems to be not much literature on detailed LiDAR identification of urban environments, the potential use of LiDAR technology in the urban environment has already been proven (Bartesaghi-Koc et al., 2019). Research on the application of LiDAR technology to generate a high resolution identification of the vertical structure of UGS confirmed its' potential to increase the accuracy of ES assessments (Casalegno et al., 2017).

In this research I set out to improve the understanding of CES provision through UGS. The creation of both a user preference map as well as a vegetation map derived from LiDAR data, will enable me to gain a novel insight into the question:

What do people like and dislike about their neighbourhood and what cultural ecosystem service activities do they use specific urban green spaces for?

The initial literature review suggests that people generally seek UGS to pursue CES activities (Jennings et al., 2016; Ko and Son, 2018). To confirm those results, and as basis for further analysis, the first hypothesis is:

People generally seek urban green spaces over other urban infrastructure to pursue cultural ecosystem service activities.

Furthermore, to link the CES to the land type diversity of UGS, I will assess the second hypothesis:

People seek urban green spaces with a high diversity of land types to pursue cultural ecosystem service activities.

Finally, I aim to make all working steps applied in this study easily replicable, to enable upscaling of the workflow to other cities and application in other research areas.

2. Theory

In the particular case of Amsterdam, where this study is performed, the municipality has recently acknowledged the importance of sustainable city development and announced the implementation of the doughnut economic model (Figure 1) (Boffey, 2020). This model aims for economical and societal fairness within the boundaries of ecological sustainability, rather than striving for unlimited growth (Raworth, 2017). This sustainable development model is based on the planetary boundaries assessment, which sets an operating space, within which humanity can impact the environment until irreversible and unpredictable damage is caused (Rockström et al., 2009). With

Figure 1: Depiction of the doughnut economic model taken from Raworth (2017), which is based on the planetary boundaries concept of Rockström et al. (2009)

targets like a 95% reduction of the cities' CO₂ emissions by 2050, Amsterdam is one of the most ambitious cities in sustainable development and could be at the forefront of innovative city development in the future. In order to achieve such goals, Amsterdam needs to find a way to accommodate a high – and increasing – density of residents, while not only decreasing CO₂ emissions within the city, but also providing social fairness to all residents.

2.1. Ecosystem services

To achieve the goal of decreasing CO₂-emissions and generally provide a healthier urban environment for residents, UGS can be of great value. Because UGS provide many services that are essential for achieving the sustainable development goals, they could be a decisive factor for the success of urban development planning. In the context of human wellbeing, the value of vegetation is commonly linked to the ecosystem services that vegetation provides (Egoh et al., 2007). Ecosystem services are divided into four main categories; supporting, regulating, provisioning and cultural (Leemans and De Groot, 2003). While supporting services (e.g. soil formation and nutrient cycling) are crucial for the provision of the three other services, those remaining three are mostly independent of each other and are commonly assessed individually (Leemans and De Groot, 2003).

Regulating ecosystem services (RES) have a stabilising impact on the environment, such as climate and water regulation (Leemans and De Groot, 2003). Because RES are essential for stable climate conditions, they are essential to a healthy urban population. On such RES that UGS provide is that they decrease flood risk by acting as a water buffer in the case of extreme rainfall (Zhang et al., 2015). Additionally, UGS regulate temperatures in cities through shade, which is especially valuable for the prevention of heat stress (Bartesaghi-Koc et al., 2019; Feyisa et al., 2014; Rui et al., 2019). The combination of quantifiability and relevance to the urban context, make RES the most researched and arguably best understood ES when it comes to the assessment of UGS (Pulighe et al., 2016).

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Provisional ecosystem services (PES) are characterised by the provision of goods, like food, fuel and fibres (Leemans and De Groot, 2003). When it comes to PES in the urban context, there seem to be differing opinions on its significance relative to other ES. On the one hand it is argued that UGS provide no significant amount of produce, which in turn means no significant impact of PES on the value of UGS (Chang et al., 2017). On the other hand urban agriculture – which is the generation of produce in the urban environment and can thus be classed under PES – in the form of community based gardens are becoming increasingly common all over Europe (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018). Urban agriculture is expected to be of importance in sustainable city development, especially in developing countries in the future, as it not only provides economic benefits through the provision of food, but also reduces CO₂-emissions through reduced transportation, decreases packaging waste and has positive educative and social impacts (Ferreira et al., 2018). However, the efficiency of urban agriculture differs strongly and some benefits like reduced CO₂-emissions are argued to be offset by factors like unfavourable growing environments, which require the usage of additional fertilizer (Mok et al., 2014). Furthermore, it has been pointed out, that the productivity of urban agriculture could be increased through built infrastructure (such as greenhouses) rather than producing crops in UGS (Gómez-Baggethun and Barton, 2013). Although the PES from urban agriculture are disputed, benefits of urban agriculture are beyond just provisioning. Research conducted in Bologna (Italy), found that factors like the educational and recreational benefits of urban agriculture are of higher importance to the citizens of Bologna than the actual produce (Sanyé-Mengual et al., 2018).

CES describe all non-material benefits that ecosystems provide, such as inspirational, educational or recreational values (Leemans and De Groot, 2003). Because CES are very vague and can come in diverse forms, some research suggests the differentiation of CES into subgroups, that describe a multitude of potential non-material benefits that people can receive from different activities performed in UGS. One such study conducted by Rall et al. (2017) that applied multiple correspondence analysis, found two main bundles of CES, dividing them into “recreational/social” and “immaterial/nature focused” (Rall et al., 2017). Another assessment on the CES provided by different types of UGS performed by Schrammeijer et al (2021, in prep), applied hierarchical clustering and found that most activities can be bundled under three main branches (Figure 2) (Schrammeijer et al., 2021, in prep).

Figure 2: Cluster dendrogram of multiple activities performed in UGS, resulting from hierarchical clustering (Schrammeijer et al., 2021). The letters A, B and C were added to the original figure to indicate the three bundles. The height indicates distance of two clusters from each other and indicates upon which distance they merged. A smaller height value indicates that the clusters are closer together.

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The findings by Schrammeijer et al. (2021, in prep) are well suited for my research, because I use the same activity categories as they did. In this study, I will use these bundles to connect CES to activities pursued in UGS. In later reference, I will call these three bundles (A) “calming”, (B) “social” and (C) “sport” (Figure 2). As a next step, it is important to investigate the CES that activities within these bundles provide.

The usage of UGS for different sport activities improves physical health, and even mental health can be positively affected by outdoor exercise (Akpınar, 2019; Tillmann et al., 2018; Wood et al., 2017). Calming activities like relaxing or enjoying nature are often connected to finding silent places and solitude, which can help residents who suffer from mental fatigue and creates opportunities for self-reflection (Arnberger, 2012; Fuller et al., 2007). Finally, UGS promote social activities like playing games or having picnics, facilitating social contact, which can promote mental health and especially in younger age groups, be of educational value (McCracken et al., 2016; Zhou and Parves Rana, 2012). Based on this evidence, I conclude that it is reasonable to make direct connections between the pursuit of certain activities and the reception of above mentioned CES.

Unfortunately, due to their intangible and hardly quantifiable nature, these inherent CES often fall short in ES assessments (Dickinson and Hobbs, 2017; Hunter and Luck, 2015). In some cases, CES of urban green spaces can be derived from demographical data. Using such data, research found out that child obesity is reduced in children that live within 500 m distance from parks (Wolch et al., 2011). Another option to assess CES is through conducting questionnaires. Using data raised from a questionnaire, Wood et al. (2017) found that higher biodiversity of the environment can improve psychological well-being (Wood et al., 2017). Quantifying reviews on CES research found that recreation and ecotourism are the most commonly studied categories of CES (Hernández-Morcillo et al., 2013; Milcu et al., 2013). Quantifiability and availability of data on ecotourism make this field better researched than other CES (Hernández-Morcillo et al., 2013). However, it was also argued that recreation and ecotourism should be considered PES, as they often pose an essential income to stakeholders (Milcu et al., 2013). For this research it is however of no further importance what ES ecotourism would be classed as, because ecotourism in general is not strongly related to cities and users of UGS are mostly residents and not tourists. To raise data on the CES provided by UGS, users must be involved and the selected population should represent the demographics of the study area as accurately as possible (Hernández-Morcillo et al., 2013).

In this research, a questionnaire was applied that included community based remote sensing. This approach enables residents to give spatial indications of what areas they value to pursue CES activities and has shown to be effective in identifying what people value about their environment (Dickinson and Hobbs, 2017).

Using such community based remote sensing will raise valuable information on the demand for CES. However it has been pointed out that many studies only assess the *demand* for UGS and fail to make the connection to the actual *supply* of UGS (Gómez-Baggethun and Barton, 2013). It is of equal importance to also analyse the UGS supply to understand precisely how UGS affects user preference (Gómez-Baggethun and Barton, 2013; Hegetschweiler et al., 2017; Lee et al., 2015). To make that connection between demand and supply, I must connect community based remote sensing to the different vegetation types present in UGS.

2.2. Urban green space types

The most general categorisation of UGS is into “green” and “grey” spaces, where “green” describes the entire vegetated infrastructure of a city and “grey” describing everything else (Hunter and Luck, 2015). However, when it comes to assessing positive impacts of UGS, mere quantification of green space is not sufficient and oversimplifies the often complex relationship between UGS and their users (Haaland and van den Bosch, 2015; Hunter and Luck, 2015).

One common approach to better assess provision of UGS is to apply categorisation techniques (using i.e. satellite data) to identify which spectral resolutions qualify as certain vegetation categories (Vatseva et al., 2016). The major downfall of such categorisation approaches is that they give no insight into the vertical structure of vegetation and either rely solely on the aerial imagery of the environment (Vatseva et al., 2016) or interpret the vertical structure of vegetation based on aerial imagery information (Huang et al., 2018). Previous reviews on UGS categorisation however, pointed out that exact detection of the vertical environment is essential to relate it to the user experience, as the user is ultimately exposed to that vertical environment (Caynes et al., 2016). This problem can be solved by using remote sensing approaches that provide more data than satellite imagery to assess vegetation. To assess the three-dimensional structure of vegetation, LiDAR is the state-of-the-art technology and is already widely used in the fields of forestry and species distribution modelling (Bakx et al., 2019; Suárez et al., 2005). LiDAR technology uses aerial vehicles to gather a three-dimensional image of a landscape using a LiDAR scanner, attached to the vehicle. By emitting light pulses, measuring the time that the light takes to return to a sensor and then translating the return time into distance, LiDAR technology captures a highly detailed picture of the terrain (Bakx et al., 2019). The emitted light can penetrate multiple layers of vegetation and measure several returns, until an impermeable surface is reached. Based on the time it takes for each reflected light pulse to return to the sensor, LiDAR technology detects the height of individual surfaces and adds them as a point to the database. The result is a point cloud that depicts the environment three dimensionally (Bakx et al., 2019). A review on the potential of LiDAR application in urban land classification found that it can increase the accuracy of such assessments by adding the vertical dimension to the land class detection and suggests complimentary usage of LiDAR information along with high resolution satellite imagery (Yan et al., 2015).

Throughout the last decade, LiDAR-based approaches to assess urban vegetation have become increasingly frequent. In many fields, the application of LiDAR was already successfully applied and was also found to be useful for the detection of urban vegetation. Han et al. (2014) succeeded in using return point intensity to identify urban vegetation, proving that it can be valuable to detect vegetation coverage of urban areas (Han et al., 2014). Other research that aimed at tree identification used LiDAR data in combination with hyperspectral imagery, which enabled not only identification of individual trees, but even differentiation of some species (Han et al., 2014; Höfle et al., 2012; Zhang and Qiu, 2012). Recently, the usage of LiDAR data to assess and quantify the diversity of UGS within a city – and even within individual green spaces – has also become more frequently researched (Bartesaghi-Koc et al., 2019; Caynes et al., 2016). Such diversity quantification is of great interest, as the methodologies applied here could be used to create a highly precise categorisation of UGS. Bartesaghi-Koc et al. (2019) combined satellite remote sensing methods and LiDAR technology to create a typology of the urban environment. To assess the surface cover, they applied a normalised difference vegetation index (NDVI), with which they could differentiate between water, pervious (irrigated and non-irrigated) and impervious surfaces. To identify the quality of the vegetation, they used LiDAR data and extracted information on the height of vegetation differentiating between high (>2 m), medium (0.5 - 2 m) and low vegetation (0-0.5 m) in the area (Bartesaghi-Koc et al., 2019). Furthermore, the researchers applied landscape metrics to assess the spatial composition of identified vegetation (Bartesaghi-Koc et al., 2019). Another approach that assessed the biomass of urban vegetation was performed by Mitchell et al. (2018), who used the three height categories, low (0 – 1 m), medium (1 – 5 m) and high (> 5 m) and extracted the return point density per height category (Mitchell et al., 2018). In their research, they coupled LiDAR data with on-site measurements of different tree species and found a correlation between their LiDAR metrics and on-site measurements (Mitchell et al., 2018). From this, the researchers conclude that usage of LiDAR metrics to predict vegetation densities, and with that urban carbon storage, has high potential.

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It was suggested that such usage of height and return point densities could be applied in combination with other remote sensing metrics to identify and differentiate vegetation in UGS with high precision and make a more accurate prediction of the vertical composition of an UGS (Caynes et al., 2016). It can be concluded that the most promising LiDAR metrics for identification of the vertical vegetation structure are height differentiation and vegetation density (Bartesaghi-Koc et al., 2019; Mitchell et al., 2018). In this research I aim to create a model that enables the typology of urban vegetation at a high resolution, by merging the methods applied by Bartesaghi-Koc et al. (2019) and Mitchell et al (2018). Furthermore, the typology will only consist of commonly understood vegetation types such as “trees”, “grass” and “meadows”, to make it easily understandable even outside the context of this work.

Finally, by combining the spatial preference indications provided by residents with the spatial composition of the vegetation in different areas, I will be able to assess how people use the UGS in their neighbourhood and if different CES activities are strongly related to certain vegetation types, land-class diversity, or in general a higher vegetation density. In this study, the classification of vegetation as well as the questionnaire on CES activities, will be performed on a case study area that covers the neighbourhood Overtoomse Veld (Amsterdam) and the surrounding parks. In this area I will then assess the vegetation preference of residents and draw conclusions on the role of UGS development in the achievement of Amsterdam’s sustainable development goals.

3. Methodology

3.1. Case study area

The case study area was chosen based on a multitude of factors (Figure 3). Fundamentally it was advantageous to conduct the research in the municipality of Amsterdam, because it enabled me to do on-site confirmation of the vegetation identification and made it possible to distribute the questionnaire through letterboxing. The Overtoomse Veld area in the West of Amsterdam was deemed ideal, as it is uniquely located between two major parks, which are comparable in size, but different in composition and design. By learning about the preference of the people living right in between these parks, it is possible to assess what vegetation composition people generally prefer and if there are UGS designs that are especially popular for certain CES activities. Furthermore the size of the area was ideal to anticipate enough questionnaire participation and have a sufficient vegetation cover and land-type diversity to assess my hypotheses.

Figure 3: The neighbourhood Overtoomse veld in Amsterdam West. The green area indicates the urban green spaces categorisation area.

3.2. Workflow

The work consisted of three main working steps: First, vegetation identification and mapping was performed, second user preferences were mapped out and third, data extraction, preparation and statistical assessment were performed. The presented workflow shows the individual working steps, upon which I will elaborate in the following chapters (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Workflow laying out the individual working steps, performed as parts of this study. The colourisation indicates what programs were used to perform the individual step, outputs with no colourisation represent data, as presented in the legend.

3.3. UGS user preference

In order to understand how the individual vegetation types relate to the preference of park users, I conducted a questionnaire. The questionnaire was prepared in collaboration with two other researchers and covered nine different areas of Amsterdam in total. The questionnaire was published through random letterboxing in the neighbourhoods in question and flyers were put up on boards in supermarkets within the different areas. People willing to participate would be redirected to the website "<https://mijnpark.environmentalgeography.nl/>" either through following the link written on it or by scanning a QR-code that was also printed on the flyers. On the website, people could inform themselves about the UGS research in general and the individual research conducted in this and the other studies that used the results. By clicking the link "doe mee/ take part", participants were then forwarded to the online questionnaire (<https://app.maptionnaire.com/nl/6768/>), in which they were asked to indicate their preferred language and the neighbourhood they relate (live, work, visit) to the strongest.

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Alongside other questions, we asked what areas participants value in their neighbourhood. Furthermore, we asked for spatial indications as to where people go in the form of either a point, path (line) or polygon indication. Once the indication was made a menu popped up that asks, “What do you usually do here?”, to which a variety of activities could be selected (Table 1). The indications of all neighbourhoods were extracted as shapefiles and clipped to the extent of my case study area. Although most indications within the case study area were made by participants indicating “Overtoomse Veld”, the data was not limited to any one neighbourhood. To display point indications, a buffer with a 30 m radius was applied. This buffer size was chosen, because perception research indicates that distances of over 30 m are perceived as far away, which we accordingly used as a threshold for the directly perceived experience of the surroundings (Swan et al., 2006). To connect indicated paths to the road network of the case study area, I applied a 15 m radius buffer to each and clipped the intersection of inputs. The road network used for clipping included all official trails in parks and was downloaded from geofabrik.de, which is a download server for data extracts from openstreetmap.nl (Geofabrik.de, 2021). Openstreetmap.nl is an open source project on which everyone can access maps for free and create new maps on voluntary basis (OpenStreetMap Nederland, 2021). Applying this clipping approach, paths that were within a 30 m distance to an actual path were picked up as indications, while paths that did not follow the actual road network were dropped and not further included in the assessment. I then merged all spatial indications into four rasters with 0.5 m resolution, including one raster for the overall CES preference, as well as one for each of the three CES bundles (Figure 2). To turn the user preference indications into a score, all spatial indications got the value “1” assigned and overlaying spatial indications were summed up. This practice was applied to the overall user preference (spatial indication, activity irrelevant), as well as to the calming, sport and social bundle, which each contained specific usage types that matched those bundles best (Table 1) (Schrammeijer et al., 2021).

Table 1: User preferences that were assigned to individual cultural ecosystem service bundles.

Bundle	Indication “What do you usually do here?”
Calm	Relax Nature Cool
Sport	Run Sport Walk Swim Cycle*
Social	Picnic/BBQ Meeting Let the children play* Walk with colleagues**

* Only a possible indication if a path was added.

** Only a possible indication if polygon or point was added.

The result was three rasters that represent the cumulative user preference to pursue social, calming or sport activities, as well as one user preference raster that represents the overall value that people put into specific areas in the case study area.

3.4. Vegetation identification

For the vegetation identification, two main data sets were used. High resolution imagery data (0.5 m resolution), which was taken by the Superview-1 satellite, was downloaded as a three-band raster (satellietdataportaal.nl, 2021). This raster was chosen as it provided the most recent high-resolution, cloudless imagery of the case study area. To identify vegetation in the case study area, NDVI (normalized difference vegetation index) was applied using ArcGIS Pro.

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This index was chosen, as it was proven to identify urban vegetation with high accuracy and is easily reproducible on different remote sensing applications (Hashim et al., 2019).

For vegetation differentiation, LiDAR data was used. The LiDAR data was called “AHN3” and gathered by Actueel Hoogtebestand Nederland (Actueel Hoogtebestand Nederland, 2021). The data is publicly available and the entire point cloud was downloaded as a LAZ-file (PDOK.nl, 2021). LiDAR data in LAZ-file form is comprised and not interoperable with many of the tools I used in this study. That is why I initially converted the LAZ-file into a LAS-file, which can be read into ArcGIS Pro and RStudio, using LAStools. Because LiDAR datasets are very large and take a long time to be processed, I first clipped the LiDAR data to the case study area using ArcGIS pro. In the next step the LiDAR data was normalised to extract a digital terrain model with highly accurate height information, and then converted into 0.5 m resolution rasters using the lidR package in RStudio. Because vegetation perception was deemed to be mostly impacted by vegetation density and height, the LAZ point cloud was transformed into rasters that provide information on the point density in different height levels. For the identification, four vegetation height levels were chosen (ground level = 0 – 0.3 m, low vegetation = 0.3 – 1 m, medium vegetation = 1 – 5 m, high vegetation 5 – 50 m). These metrics were partly derived from the methodology applied by Mitchel et al. (2018), who used the height levels 0–1 m to identify understory, 1–5 to identify presence of medium high vegetation and > 5 m to identify high vegetation like trees (Mitchell et al., 2018). The height level 0.3 – 1 m was added, as it enabled differentiation between grass and meadows in the urban environment, which was a useful addition for this research.

Finally, the number of returns per pixel and height level was used to determine the vegetation density and vertical structure of the vegetation. Based on these parameters, seven vegetation categories were extracted (Table 2). The rasters were converted into vegetation categories using ArcGIS pro.

Table 2: Vegetation types and the parameters by which they were determined.

Vegetation type	Height levels detected	Number of returns
Grass	Ground level	*
Meadow	(All lower height levels) + Low vegetation	*
Bushland	(All lower height levels) + Medium vegetation	*
Trees	(All lower height levels) + High vegetation	*
Trees and meadows	(All lower height levels) + Low and High vegetations + no returns on Medium vegetation	*
Trees and bushland (scarce)	(All lower height levels) + Medium and High vegetation	High vegetation < 10 returns
Trees and bushland (dense)	(Any lower classes) + Medium and High vegetation	High vegetation > 10 returns

*The height levels alone determined the vegetation category.

Because height level proved to be the most efficient factor to differentiate between vegetation categories accurately, the return point density per 0.5 m was only applied to higher vegetation classes. For those, the difference in return point densities indicated whether they are categorised as dense or scarce vegetation. Using both remote sensing analysis and on-site observations, it was decided that the threshold of 10 return points per 0.5 m pixel is ideal as a cut off between dense and scarce vegetation. The category “trees” is kept general, because it mostly resembles all trees that have only grass underneath, however in some densely vegetated areas the “tree” type also applied to pixels that have vegetation underneath. This is caused by the emitted light not penetrating the vegetation to height levels lower than ten meters, which causes all returns to indicate the vegetation type “tree”. Additionally, for the analysis of land-type diversity, I created a land class map to which I added “water” and “non-vegetated areas”. Waterbodies were rasterised from a polygon. The data was extracted from openstreetmaps.com and downloaded from the download server geofabrik.de (Geofabrik.de, 2021). All pixels within the case study area that were neither classified as “water” or one of the identified vegetation types, were afterwards assigned the category “non-vegetated areas”.

3.5. Spatial statistics

To enable statistical comparison of the vegetation map and the user CES preference map, I divided both maps into one-hectare (100 x 100 m) sized tiles. Tiles of one-hectare size proved ideal to provide a good representation of the vegetation cover and diversity, while still providing sufficient samples for statistical analysis. On those tiles I performed spatial statistics using Fragstats (v4.2.1). I calculated the percentage of land (PLAND) that was covered by vegetation relative to non-vegetated area per tile, as well as the PLAND of all individual vegetation categories of each tile. I then extracted the Simpson's index of diversity (SIDI) of each tile (Simpson, 1949). The SIDI was performed on the land class map to ensure that the entire area of a tile is taken into consideration. Simpson's index of diversity was chosen as it is a very accurate diversity measure that is robust to low and differing input sample sizes (Magurran, 2013). The value of the SIDI represents the probability that any two pixels selected randomly within a defined area would be different patch types. Thus, the highest possible diversity that can be measured is "1" and if there is only one class the value will be "0", as there is then no chance of ever getting two pixels with different land-types. The user preference map was divided by the same one-hectare tiles and the PLAND of individual user scores was extracted. For further analysis the PLAND of individual user scores was transformed into the proportion (= PLAND of user scores / 100). From the different user scores and the relative proportion they cover per tile, I extracted one user preference score (UPS). This was done by multiplying the user score with its relative proportion and summing up all products of a specific tile to one overall tile score (Formula 1). The proportion of land per tile that had no user preference indication was multiplied by zero to indicate that these areas did not add to the overall CES perception. Finally, I created a normalised user preference score (NUPS), to enable representable cross comparison between bundles and overall preference (Formula 2).

$$(1) \text{ UPS:} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{TileID} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ X \mapsto \text{UPS}_X := \sum_{i=1}^n (\text{UserScore}_X^i \times \text{proportion}_X^i) \end{array}$$

$$(2) \text{ NUPS:} \quad \begin{array}{l} \text{TileID} \rightarrow \mathbb{R} \\ X \mapsto \text{NUPS}_X := \frac{(\text{UPS}_X - \min(\text{UPS}))}{(\max(\text{UPS}) - \min(\text{UPS}))} \times 100 \end{array}$$

To answer the question of whether people seek UGS over other urban infrastructure to pursue CES activities, I applied linear regression using RStudio. Here the null hypothesis was "There is no significant relationship between the vegetation cover and the NUPS.". The input data sets were the NUPS as dependent (y) and respective the PLAND of vegetation as independent variable (x) of all tiles. Additionally, I assessed the impact that the PLAND of vegetation had on the NUPS related to the individual CES bundles.

To find out if people seek UGS with a high diversity of categories to pursue CES activities, I applied linear regression to find out what effect the SIDI (x) has on the NUPS (y). Here the null hypothesis was "There is no significant relationship between the Simpsons diversity index and the NUPS.". Furthermore, I assessed the impact of the SIDI on the NUPS of the three CES bundles individually.

Throughout the entire statistical assessment, the threshold to discard the null hypothesis was $p < 0.05$.

Finally, to answer the overarching research question: "What do people like and dislike about their neighbourhood and what cultural ecosystem service activities do they use specific vegetation for?", I performed multiple stepwise regression on all bundles to identify if individual vegetation categories have a strong effect on user preference.

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To determine the best fitting model, the R^2 , as well as the Akaike information criteria (AIC) were taken into consideration. The R^2 was used as primary factor, where a high R^2 indicates a good fit. If the highest detected R^2 was similar for several models, the AIC was conducted to determine which model fits best. For the AIC a lower value indicates a higher significance. All statistical assessments on the finalised datasets as well as creation of graphs were performed in RStudio.

3.6. Reference to data storage

In order to enable reproducibility and provide as much transparency in my work as possible, my data handling will follow the FAIR data principles. The FAIR stand for findability, accessibility, interoperability and reusability and was created as a framework for data handling to improve the scholarly infrastructure (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

To do so, I created a community on zenodo.org, with the name “The cultural ecosystem services provided by different types of urban green spaces” (<https://zenodo.org/communities/ugs-ces-relationships/>). Zenodo.org is an open science website, that was created to enable everyone to share their research findings (European Organization For Nuclear Research and OpenAIRE, 2013). The reason I chose Zenodo over other platforms is that communities have no data size limits and individual uploads can be of up to 50 GB size, which enables me to upload all input data used in this study. All my inputs, interim outputs, final outputs as well as code scripts and models created in the individual programs (Figure 4) will be shared in this openly accessible platform. Furthermore, other researchers working on the wider topic “relationship between cultural ecosystem services and urban green spaces”, are invited to join this community to pose questions, start discussions or share their own data in this community.

Finally, all spatial data (including satellite imagery and LiDAR data) used for the creation of the vegetation typology is publicly available online and is thus easily accessible. The model to map questionnaire indication was created in such a way, that new questionnaire inputs can be mapped out by only changing the input data and running the model.

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4. Results

4.1. Mapping results

As part of this research, six maps were created. Two land classification maps were created, one of which contains information on the vegetation cover and vegetation type composition in the case study area, the other representing a land use classification, which includes the land types “water” and “non-vegetated areas”. The other four show the indications that people gave as to where they pursue CES activities. One shows the overall user preference map and the other three show, the sport, social and calming CES preferences respectively.

The vegetation type map contains seven vegetation categories. The identification was performed at a 0.5 m resolution (Figure 5). I detected 205.1 ha of vegetation in the case study area. Of all categories detected, grass is the most common, covering 96.2 ha of the case study area. The second most common category is trees with 62.8 ha. The remaining five categories each cover less than ten percent of the detected vegetated area, with trees and meadows representing the least common type covering just over 1.09% of the vegetated area. In the second map, which includes a classification of the entire case study area, the land types “non-vegetated areas” and “water” each cover a bigger area than the most commonly identified vegetation type (Annex).

Figure 5: The vegetation type map of Overtoomse Veld, as derived from satellite and LiDAR data.

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The user preference map (Figure 6) was exported from ArcGIS as a raster file and contains all spatial indications that users made. The highest number of overlapping indications was found in Rembrandt park, east in the map. Areas within the case study area that were never indicated by questionnaire participants were set to be zero for the statistical assessment.

The spatial indications concentrated strongly on the two parks on the east and west side of the case study area, with only a few indications within the built environment of the neighbourhood in the centre of the map. The highest number of spatially overlapping indications was 44 indications which occurred along paths within the Rembrandtpark in the east of the case study area.

Figure 6: The overall user preference map of the case study area. The number (1 – 44) indicates the count of spatial indications that overlapped on any 0.5 m particular pixel.

The other three maps were created using the indications for the individual CES bundles sport, calming and social individually (Annex).

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4.2. Vegetation cover preference

Linear regression between the user preference and the average vegetation cover per tile showed a significant positive relationship ($P = 3.2511 \cdot 10^{-56}$) (Figure 7). Overall a strong positive trend can be observed ($+ 0.508 x$). It is important to note that this assessment encompasses all tiles within the case study area. Tiles that did not overlap with any user preference indications have the value zero.

It is interesting to note, that tiles with a low vegetation cover received overall low NUPS, with not a single tile that had less than 50% vegetation cover and a NUPS of over 50 (Figure 7).

Comparing the three CES bundles relative to the vegetation cover of a tile also showed overall positive relationships (Figure 8). In this regression analysis I only included tiles that contained user indications. So this figure compares areas that were used for CES activities, hence the value "0" here indicates the tile with the lowest UPS per CES bundle.

Figure 7: Normalised user preference score relative to the vegetation cover. Every point represents one tile that fell within the case study area.

Figure 8: Normalised user preference scores of different CES bundles relative to the vegetation cover. Points represent tiles that fell within the case study area and contained spatial indications for the individual CES bundle.

Interestingly, the NUPS of the calming bundle showed a strong positive trend ($+ 0.677 x$) with increasing vegetation cover and the lowest variance of all bundles ($R^2 = 0.26$). Regression analysis showed that the NUPS of the calming bundle significantly correlates to the vegetation cover ($P = 0.000207$). The sport bundle also showed a positive trend ($+ 0.484 x$), but a stronger variance than the calming bundle ($R^2 = 0.13$). Despite the high variance, a significant relationship between vegetation cover and NUPS of the sport bundle exists ($P = 0.01416$). The NUPS for the social bundle only shows a minimally positive trend in relation to vegetation cover ($+ 0.136 x$) and tiles show the strongest variance among all bundles ($R^2 = 0.01$). The bundle for social values shows no significant relationship between vegetation cover increase and the NUPS ($P = 0.4712$).

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4.3. Land-type diversity preference

The performance of linear regression on the NUPS and SIDI showed that there is a significant correlation between land-class diversity and the NUPS (Figure 9). The correlation analysis shows a significant ($P = 6.2887 \times 10^{-30}$) positive correlation ($+ 56.2 x$) between the NUPS and the SIDI. This indicates that the NUPS increases with higher land-class diversity. Here, all tiles that fell into the case study area were included in the assessment. Interestingly, it seems like the NUPS stagnates once a SIDI of "0.75" is reached. In contrast, NUPS higher than "75" do not even exceed a SIDI of "0.75".

Figure 9: Land-type diversity measured using the simpson's diversity index, in relation to the normalised user preference score. Each point represents one tile within the case study area.

The assessment on the impact of the SIDI on individual CES found no significant increase of user preference with a change in SIDI (Figure 10).

In the assessment per CES bundle, only tiles that included a spatial indication for the respective CES bundle were considered. For sport ($P = 0.889$), social ($P = 0.1497$) and calming ($P = 0.3187$) activities no correlation between the relative NUPS and SIDI was found. Furthermore none of the bundles show a strong tendency that SIDI has a positive or negative impact on relative NUPS, however it is worth mentioning that sport was the only bundle that showed a negative trend ($- 3.58 x$) with an increasing SIDI.

Figure 10: Land-type diversity measured using simpson's diversity index in comparison to the normalised user preference score of the three CES bundles sport, social and calming.

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4.4. Individual vegetation type preference

Finally, I investigated the individual vegetation types and assessed if there is a significant relationship between the presence of one vegetation type and user preference. The multiple stepwise regression found for all CES bundles that a multitude of vegetation types increases R^2 , which indicates that a multitude of vegetation types is better suited than individual vegetation types to explain the why users prefer certain areas within the case study area (Annex).

For the sport bundle, the best fitting model was found to contain all seven vegetation types ($R^2 = 0.4228$) (Annex, Table 3). The social bundle also showed the best fit for a model that contained all seven vegetation types ($R^2 = 0.3479$) (Annex, Table 4). In contrast, the calming bundle showed that the best fitting model only consists of the five vegetation types “grass”, “trees”, “bushland”, “trees and meadow” and “trees and bushes dense” ($R^2 = 0.4951$, AIC = 442.0965) (Annex, Table 5). This indicates that the vegetation types “meadow” as well as “trees and bushland scarce” were not suited improve the prediction of the overall user preference for calming activities. To further assess how individual vegetation types related to user preferences, I performed linear regression on all bundles and vegetation types and visualised all vegetation types that significantly correlated with the NUPS of the individual bundles.

For the sport bundle, I found that trees ($P = 0.02761$) and meadows ($P = 0.04354$) are the only vegetation types that have a significant individual impact on the NUPS (Figure 11 A & B). While trees have a positive impact on the NUPS (+ 0.578 x) (Figure 11 B), interestingly with increasing meadow cover of the landscape, the NUPS decreased (- 3.34 x) (Figure 11 A).

Figure 11: Vegetation types that show a significant relationship between the NUPS of the sport bundle and vegetation type cover. On the left, the graph for meadows and on the right the graph for trees is shown.

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For the calming bundle, I also found two vegetation types positively correlating with the NUPS. Here the types trees and meadow ($P = 0.022488$) and dense trees and bushes ($P = 0.043644$) had a significant impact on the NUPS (Figure 12 A, B). Trees and meadows negatively correlate with NUPS ($- 17.1 x$) (Figure 12 A), while dense trees and bushes show a positive relationship ($+ 2.04 x$) (Figure 12 B).

Figure 12: Vegetation types that show a significant relationship between the NUPS of the calming bundle and vegetation type cover. On the left, the graph for trees and meadows (A) and on the right the graph for dense trees and bushes (B) is shown.

Lastly the assessment on social values found that only dense trees and bushes significantly correlate with the NUPS (Figure 13). Similar to the results for sport activities, there is a significant relationship between the NUPS and the relative cover of dense bushes and trees ($P = 0.0084527$) and the relationship between the factors is positive ($+ 2.37 x$). All other vegetation types were not found to significantly correlate with the NUPS of the different CES bundles.

Scatterplots depicting the impact of all vegetation types on the three CES bundles individually are available in the annex (Figure 17).

Figure 13: Linear regression between dense tree and shrub cover and NUPS for social activities.

5. Discussion

5.1. Influence of vegetation cover on user preference

In this research I successfully applied a novel methodology towards assessing what people value about UGS. The results show that people indeed prefer higher vegetation densities to pursue CES activities in general, and in particular, activities summarised under the calming and sport bundle showed a strong positive relationship. Based on these findings I conclude that hypothesis one – “People generally seek urban green spaces over other urban infrastructure to pursue cultural ecosystem service activities” – can be confirmed, but with the limitation that social activities in particular are likely more strongly affected by other factors. The findings that people generally prefer overall higher vegetation densities to pursue CES activities, aligns with what previous research found (Dickinson and Hobbs, 2017; Rall et al., 2017). Additionally however, my findings show that areas with less than 50% vegetation cover never scored a NUPS of higher than 50%. Investigating this relationship further by comparing the numbers to the vegetation map (Figure 5), shows that most areas with less than 50% vegetation cover within the case study area are trees along roads and other informal green spaces between housing districts. This indicates that the user preference had a strong tendency towards the two big parks over informal green spaces, which can also be seen in the user preference map (Figure 6). Whether this tendency towards larger UGS such as parks for CES activities can be generalised is still a disputed topic in research. On the one hand, studies on the recreational values of parks found an overall preference for larger UGS, stating that they need to be of sufficient size and structure to prevent “urban intrusion” into the nature experience (Coles and Bussey, 2000; Massoni et al., 2018)). On the other hand, Massoni et al. (2018) argue that the size of an UGS is not of significance for its provision of CES, but that the structure of an UGS is a stronger determinators on how UGS are perceived. Additionally, they mentioned that user preferences for UGS are highly heterogenous, which implies that the preference fluctuate strongly depending on who you ask (Massoni et al., 2018). Both studies, as well as multiple reviews (Gómez-Baggethun and Barton, 2013; Haaland and van den Bosch, 2015; Hunter and Luck, 2015), called for better differentiation between the social aspects of UGS alongside the natural aspects to improve understanding on differences found in vegetation preference. With the differentiation of CES into the three bundles, I was able to add this social differentiation to my UGS assessment and gain further insight into the vegetation cover preferences. I found that there is indeed a difference in the importance of vegetation cover between the different CES bundles. While people who pursued calming activities indicated areas with increasing vegetation cover more often, people pursuing social activities seemed to be more indifferent as to how dense the vegetation cover in their surroundings is. This shows that while the size of UGS may indeed matter for the performance of some CES activities, like Coles and Bussey (2000) suggested, for social activities this may be of less relevance. For social activities, values like the structure of vegetation or impacts of other infrastructure could be of higher value. Adding to this, recent research found that non-vegetated areas that facilitate sitting or doing sports were found to be positively associated with social activities in UGS (Palliwoda and Priess, 2021). This provides further evidence that the differentiation into CES bundles is of great value for the understanding of what people value about their UGS and furthermore shows that the differentiation into the three CES activity bundles (sport, calming and social) is an efficient way of differentiating between preferences.

5.2. Influence of land-type diversity on user preference

When it comes to land type diversity, it is interesting to see that a high diversity of land use types has an overall positive impact on the perceived value of the urban environment. However, the detailed assessment on the three individual CES bundles found no correlation. Based on these findings I conclude that hypothesis two – “People seek urban green spaces with a high diversity of land types to pursue cultural ecosystem service activities” – was confirmed, but no CES bundle-specific conclusions could be drawn.

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It is in this context important to mention that vegetation type diversity is different to biodiversity, which is often used to assess genetic, organismal or ecological diversity of an area (Heywood and Watson, 1995). This assessment only considered the diversity of land use types identified and is thus not easily comparable to other biodiversity assessments. It must thus be considered independent of biodiversity assessments on UGS, which often relate biodiversity to improved CES provision (Aronson et al., 2017; Y. Wang et al., 2019). Despite this limitation, there are some interesting studies that investigated vegetation type diversity, which also found a positive correlation between land type diversity and user preference (Vierikko et al., 2020). Vierikko et al. (2020) used biotopes, vegetation structure, facilities and services as well as artificial elements as structural characteristics to identify the structural diversity of UGS in Europe (Vierikko et al., 2020). In the study performed by Vierikko et al. (2020), they present an interesting approach towards assessing the overall diversity of parks. However, their classification does not consider diversity differences within the UGS and does not enable fine diversity analysis throughout an entire neighbourhood or within a park. The study created here, adds to this existing body of knowledge that also the diversity on a small scale within UGS contributes to the preference of UGS users. The addition of “water” to the vegetation types proved useful, as much research on the value of UGS mentioned that the existence of waterbodies within a UGS may also positively affect the overall “nature” experience and should thus be included in UGS diversity assessments of any kind (R. Wang et al., 2019).

5.3. Significance of individual vegetation types on user preference

For individual vegetation types, the stepwise multiple regression showed that overall higher numbers of vegetation types are more accurate at predicting the NUPS (Annex). The only exception were calming activities, which were best explained when meadows as well as scarce trees and bushes were removed from the model (Annex). This indicates that people pursuing calming activities are indifferent to meadows as well as scarce trees and bushland. To furthermore find out which vegetation types have a significant positive or negative impact on the NUPS, I performed linear regression on all vegetation types and the respective CES bundles individually. This approach found a total of five significant relationships between individual vegetation and the NUPS of the CES bundles.

Interestingly, trees have a positive impact for an area to be used for sport activities (Figure 11 A). This could be caused by shading that the trees provide, which may be a preferred environment for the performance of sport activities, as shade from trees decreases urban heat stress (Feyisa et al., 2014). Meadows on the other hand were found to negatively affect the user preference for sport activities (Figure 11 B). The fact that meadows were negatively related is at first surprising, as past research suggested that meadows were found to be positively perceived by users of UGS (Southon et al., 2017). One reason for this contrasting result could be that that meadows in this research were regarded as a separate vegetation type than grass, which means that meadows in this research were only identified as such if vegetation was higher than ten cm. In contrast to the lower vegetation type grass, meadows may thus not facilitate sport activities like running as well.

For calming activities, people liked to visit areas that provided a lot of dense tree and bushland cover (Figure 12 A). This is likely linked to the sense of tranquillity and out-of-the-city feeling that such dense trees were found to provide (McKinney and VerBerkmoes, 2020). Beside that I found that trees and meadows negatively affect the preference for pursuing calming activities. While this seems counterintuitive, potentially a lack of seating possibilities and high abundance of insects in such areas could be one reason that causes this relationship.

Finally, for pursuing social activities, a significant relationship to dense trees and bushes was found. Considering that I found no significant impact of overall vegetation cover on the preference for social activities, this result is surprising as it shows that people seek dense vertical vegetation structures to pursue social activities, while not prioritizing overall high vegetation cover.

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This could be related to the fact that social activities are more often connected to non-vegetated areas within green spaces (Palliwoda and Priess, 2021), but comes to show that even for social activities, more dense vegetation is preferred over scarce vegetation.

Overall, these results suggest that people have a tendency towards dense vegetation structures that contain high vegetation, such as trees over lower vegetation like grass and meadows. The assessment of user preference on individual vegetation types provides interesting new insights and although a multitude of vegetation types showed to be more strongly correlated to the individual CES bundles (Annex), this highly detailed analysis provides a strong tool to understand CES provided by UGS better.

5.4. Mapping approach success and room for improvement

I found that the creation of maps to assess the CES provided by UGS is a very good approach to improving the understanding of CES provided by UGS. Using a questionnaire and mapping the spatial indications proved highly effective and enabled a highly accurate prediction of which areas people use to pursue CES activities.

Furthermore, the vegetation and land use type detection were performed successfully, and the usage of LiDAR extracted data proved efficient for the identification of vegetation. One downfall of the categorisation is that trees had to be detected as a generic class without clear indication of the vegetation that lays underneath. This is because for those pixels, all values were higher than five meters, which is caused by the light pulses emitted by the LiDAR sensor not penetrating through the canopy and happens especially often in dense canopy layers (Li et al., 2011). To solve this issue and increase the precision of the vegetation typology, addition of more parameters can be considered. Vizzari and Sigura (2015) used a multitude of existing data sets such as land use data and the Simpson's evenness index to identify different landscape types (Vizzari and Sigura, 2015). Although their approach was performed on urban and rural environments at a lower resolution, such analysis as a basis upon which further parameters could be added to the vegetation identification model, could be a step towards estimating the vegetation underneath trees. Another solution could be smoothing the landscape. The smoothing steps performed on the presented maps filled "no data" pixels with the value of the most commonly adjacent pixel, however Clark et al. (2004) suggested that smoothing of the vegetation detected under a canopy using kriging interpolation could be used to more accurately predict sub-canopy vegetation (Clark et al., 2004). Finally, lowering the resolution from 0.5 m to 1 m or even 5 m, should be considered as this may decrease the chance of receiving no data from under the canopy. However, in this case the trade-off in resolution loss must be considered.

Despite this room for improvement, the vegetation type identification was accurate and efficient for the assessment of vegetation type preferences. To make it possible to upscale these mapping models to larger areas or to other contexts, they were created to only require a change of input data to apply the vegetation typology as well as the user preference mapping to other contexts. The transformation of LiDAR data into rasters in an early working step, reduces the computation times significantly, but normalisation of extensive LiDAR point clouds still requires immense computational power.

5.5. Possible improvements and outlook for future research

For future research, an interesting addition to the differentiation into social bundles could be to include age groups in a questionnaire. This would not only make it possible to relate age specific preferences to UGS, but also enable urban planners to incorporate UGS preferences better to different demographics living in the area. Research differentiating between age groups, already found that there are some age specific differences and proved a useful tool to explain differences in UGS usage (Palliwoda and Priess, 2021). Furthermore, similar to age group specific UGS preference research, it would be beneficial to also consider cultural and ethnic as well as economic prosperity differences, as such factors may also significantly impact how people use UGS (Boulton et al., 2018).

Discussion

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The land type diversity was a useful tool to get an overall understanding on how the abundance of different land types affects user preference. Unfortunately, because the assessment on the spatial composition of vegetation within a plot was not within the frame of this work, the results give no indication as to what impact the vegetation structure within an UGS has. To include this spatial composition in future research, the methodology applied by Bartesaghi-Koc et al. (2019) could be of great value. They created an urban typology by including LiDAR derived vegetation information and combined it with analysis on the spatial composition of vegetation structure within plots to categorise the entire urban environment by vegetation density and structure (Bartesaghi-Koc et al., 2019). The questionnaire proved highly efficient to gather data on spatial user preferences and similar assessments should consider such analysis for future research. One improvement to more precisely map user preferences could be to increase the accuracy of path indications. To avoid loss of data through clipping approaches like I performed in this study, the line indications should already be linked to an underlying road network. This could be achieved by applying a road network tool that automatically links indicated start, way and end points to the most logical route along a provided street network, which exists in ArcGIS Pro and shows promise to increase the accuracy of path indications (Sevtsuk and Mekonnen, 2012). The differentiation into CES bundles based on (Schrammeijer et al., 2021, in prep.) was found to be a useful application, however, for bigger datasets the assessment of individual activities over bundles should be considered to increase the accuracy of a study even further. Finally, more research applying methodologies like the one presented here that break both, the vegetation provision as well as the activity types down into subgroups should be conducted. It provides a valuable approach to accurately predict the CES that UGS provide and could enable urban planners to optimise implementation of UGS into future urban development planning.

6. Conclusion

This study proposes a new methodology towards assessing CES provided by UGS. The differentiation between CES activities into the three bundles (calming, sport and social), proved efficient for more accurate differentiation on user preferences and enabled improved analysis of the spatial preference for different kinds of activities. Furthermore, the application of LiDAR data to identify vegetation types within an urban environment provides further evidence that LiDAR data can be of great help in assessing the vertical structure of vegetation, with some limitations in areas with dense canopy cover. These results enabled the assessment of the provision of different vegetation densities, land type diversities and even individual vegetation types. In addition, it was possible to link these parameters to the demand for specific CES activities. The results found that people prefer areas with high vegetation cover and diverse vegetation types, which aligns with what previous research suggested and provides evidence that the methodology applied here accurately assesses user preferences. On top of that I found that different CES bundles have different preferences for vegetation cover of the area and even for individual vegetation types. This new insight may be a valuable addition to the existing body of knowledge, as it provides further evidence that CES should not be analysed as only one class, but that different activities and their inherent benefits need to be grouped and assessed individually. Although it will be important to create links between individual CES bundles and demographical groups and refine vegetation identification, this research provides a first step towards understanding the value of UGS better and enables the connection of such preferences to the vegetation within the urban environment. Application of such differentiation between CES and identifying how vegetation type, structure and diversity cater to them individually, will be essential for future urban planning to create better UGS and make cities more liveable. In light of the increasing urban population densities worldwide, it will be of utmost importance to maintain and improve existing UGS and incorporate them in future city development. Conclusively, the UGS management approach that Amsterdam will follow may be decisive for their success in achieving their sustainable urban development goals in the future.

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Annex

Land classification maps

Maps displaying the vegetation categorisation map (Figure 14) and the land-type map (Figure 15), which includes the categories “water” and “non-vegetated areas”.

Figure 14: The vegetation type map of Overtoomse Veld, as derived from satellite and LiDAR data.

Annex

The cultural ecosystem services provided by different types of urban green spaces

Marlon Sippel

CES bundle maps

Maps displaying the user preference maps for the overall user preference and the three CES bundles “Sport”, “Social” and “Calming” (Figure 16).

Figure 16: Maps depicting the user preference indications for the overall user preference (top left), and the three cultural ecosystem service bundles sport (top right), social (bottom left) and calming (bottom right).

Multiple stepwise regression results

Best Subsets Regression sport bundle:

Model	Predictors
1	Trees
2	Bushland Trees_and_bushes_scarce
3	Bushland Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_scarce
4	Bushland Trees_and_meadow Meadow Trees_and_bushes_scarce
5	Grass Bushland Trees_and_meadow Meadow Trees_and_bushes_scarce
6	Grass Trees Bushland Meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense Trees_and_bushes_scarce
7	Grass Trees Bushland Trees_and_meadow Meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense Trees_and_bushes_scarce

Table 3: Subsets regression summary containing the different models for the sport bundle. The model number indicates how many vegetation parameters were put into the model. The Akaike information criteria were used as a measure of significance, in which a lower AIC indicated higher significance.

Model	R-Square	Adj. R-Square	Pred. R-Square	C(p)	AIC	SBIC	SBC	MSEP	FPE	HSP	APC
1	0.1103	0.0891	0.0156	15.4855	407.0394	281.2591	412.392	24524.196	582.6736	13.5937	0.9744
2	0.2717	0.2361	0.1423	7.4236	400.2355	275.1789	407.3722	20578.8306	499.267	11.685	0.8349
3	0.3796	0.3331	0.252	2.6903	395.176	271.3696	404.097	17977.8157	445.165	10.4633	0.7444
4	0.381	0.3175	0.1515	4.6051	397.0789	273.5708	407.7841	18410.2492	465.0642	10.9897	0.7777
5	0.3838	0.3027	0.0527	6.4307	398.8797	275.7102	411.369	18822.4092	484.8435	11.5314	0.8108
6	0.4135	0.3184	-1.00E-04	6.579	398.7069	276.5983	412.9805	18413.1621	483.4344	11.5856	0.8084
7	0.4228	0.3105	-1.00E-04	8	400.0049	278.5951	416.0626	18639.4673	498.5866	12.0537	0.8338

AIC: Akaike Information Criteria

SBIC: Sawa's Bayesian Information Criteria

SBC: Schwarz Bayesian Criteria

MSEP: Estimated error of prediction, assuming multivariate normality

FPE: Final Prediction Error

HSP: Hocking's Sp

APC: Amemiya Prediction Criteria

Annex

The cultural ecosystem services provided by different types of urban green spaces

Marlon Sippel

Best Subsets Regression social bundle

Model	Predictors
1	Trees_and_bushes_dense
2	Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense
3	Bushland Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense
4	Grass Trees Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense
5	Grass Bushland Trees_and_meadow Meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense
6	Grass Bushland Trees_and_meadow Meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense Trees_and_bushes_scarce
7	Grass Trees Bushland Trees_and_meadow Meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense Trees_and_bushes_scarce

Table 4: Subsets regression summary containing the different models for the social bundle. The model number indicates how many vegetation parameters were put into the model. The Akaike information criteria were used as a measure of significance, in which a lower AIC indicated higher significance.

Model	R-Square	Adj. R-Square	Pred. R-Square	C(p)	AIC	SBIC	SBC	MSEP	FPE	HSP	APC
1	0.1283	0.1112	0.0627	11.1573	501.1796	350.2679	507.0905	36824.6101	721.0024	13.8957	0.9401
2	0.2431	0.2128	0.1652	5.234	495.6945	345.3746	503.5757	32627.0212	650.171	12.558	0.8477
3	0.2911	0.2477	0.2049	3.922	494.2227	344.4682	504.0742	31194.8713	632.469	12.2518	0.8246
4	0.3345	0.279	0.2166	2.9297	492.8775	343.962	504.6992	29909.9101	616.7878	11.9918	0.8042
5	0.34	0.2698	0.2075	4.5461	494.433	345.9359	508.2251	30304.9279	635.4206	12.4087	0.8285
6	0.3457	0.2603	0.1612	6.1568	495.9781	347.9419	511.7404	30713.5789	654.5946	12.8494	0.8535
7	0.3479	0.2465	0.1361	8	497.7937	350.1675	515.5263	31302.5446	677.9313	13.3869	0.8839

AIC: Akaike Information Criteria

SBIC: Sawa's Bayesian Information Criteria

SBC: Schwarz Bayesian Criteria

MSEP: Estimated error of prediction, assuming multivariate normality

FPE: Final Prediction Error

HSP: Hocking's Sp

APC: Amemiya Prediction Criteria

Best Subsets Regression of calming bundle

Model	Predictors
1	Trees_and_meadow
2	Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense
3	Bushland Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense
4	Grass Bushland Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense
5	Grass Trees Bushland Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense
6	Grass Trees Bushland Trees_and_meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense Trees_and_bushes_scarce
7	Grass Trees Bushland Trees_and_meadow Meadow Trees_and_bushes_dense Trees_and_bushes_scarce

Table 5: Subsets regression summary containing the different models for the sport bundle. The model number indicates how many vegetation parameters were put into the model. The Akaike information criteria were used as a measure of significance, in which a lower AIC indicated higher significance.

Model	R-Square	Adj. R-Square	Pred. R-Square	C(p)	AIC	SBIC	SBC	MSEP	FPE	HSP	APC
1	0.1081	0.0887	0.0403	26.659	461.404 5	323.698	467.018 1	38696.922 1	839.744 6	17.9146	0.9694
2	0.3828	0.3554	0.3031	6.8978	445.734 1	309.405 1	453.218 9	27387.842 1	605.918 5	12.9608	0.6995
3	0.4652	0.4287	0.3891	2.3736	440.860 1	305.669	450.216 1	24285.566 3	547.537	11.7539	0.6321
4	0.4707	0.4215	0.3402	3.9323	442.357 7	307.544 7	453.584 9	24604.887 1	565.098 5	12.1854	0.6524
5	0.4951	0.435	0.3518	4.0028	442.096 5	308.197 5	455.194 9	24045.185 9	562.344 6	12.1918	0.6492
6	0.4951	0.4212	0.3224	6.0002	444.093 4	310.595 2	459.063	24644.697 7	586.689 6	12.8005	0.6773
7	0.4951	0.4068	0.3103	8	446.093 2	312.995 1	462.934	25276.502 2	612.287 9	13.4569	0.7068

AIC: Akaike Information Criteria

SBIC: Sawa's Bayesian Information Criteria

SBC: Schwarz Bayesian Criteria

MSEP: Estimated error of prediction, assuming multivariate normality

FPE: Final Prediction Error

HSP: Hocking's Sp

APC: Amemiya Prediction Criteria

Relationship between vegetation types and CES bundles

Figure 17: Scatterplots depicting the relationship of each vegetation type to the individual cultural ecosystem service specific normalised user preference score.